

Imaging the Life-Cycle of CMCs Using High-Resolution X-ray Computed Tomography

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This work was supported by the **University of Utah**, the **Advanced Light Source**, and the **AFRL Summer Faculty Fellowship Program**.

Overview:

- CMCs exhibit excellent performance in **extreme thermo-mechanical-oxidative environments**
- Establishing a relationship among manufacturing, resulting microstructure, and damage of CMCs remains a significant challenge

Objective:

- Use high-resolution X-ray micro-tomography (μ CT) and *in situ* testing to image and study the **entire life-cycle of CMCs**

- Material system and experimental approach
- CMC fabrication and imaging
- Manual and automatic segmentation
- Analysis of porosity
- Conclusions and future work

USAF X-51A Waverider
Source: USAF

GE LEAP engine
Source: GE Aviation

Materials and experimental approach

Material system and fabrication:

- CG Nicalon 8HS satin weave fabric
- SMP-10 matrix
- $[0/90]_{2S}$ stacking sequence
- Polymer infiltration and pyrolysis (PIP)
 - Pyrolysis is performed at 1000°C
 - 5 subsequent re-infiltrations

Experimental approach:

- Use AFRL's Xradia XRM-520 μCT system to **image evolution of the microstructure** during the PIP process
 - $1.26\ \mu\text{m}/\text{voxel}$ size with a 38 h scan time
- Perform ***in situ* mechanical testing** at the ALS in realistic conditions (1000°C in humid air)
 - $1.30\ \mu\text{m}/\text{voxel}$ size with a 30 min scan time

Polymer infiltration and pyrolysis (PIP)

Image acquisition and segmentation

Imaging:

- 22.1 (AFRL) to 43 (ALS) GBs and 2000 images per data set

Over **1TB** of raw image data has been collected over the course of **two years**

Segmentation:

- Semi-automatic segmentation of fiber-tows in Avizo
- Automatic image pre-processing and segmentation of porosity using machine learning (WEKA 3, Waikato University)

Image data

2D cross-section

3D ROI after
C-stage

Evolution of the microstructure during PIP

Evolution of the microstructure during PIP

C-stage

Pyrolysis

PIP 1

PIP 2

PIP 3

PIP 4

PIP 5

Pre-test sample

Evolution of the microstructure during PIP

C-stage

Pre-test

Able to capture the same ROI throughout the manufacturing process and visualize persistent pores

Evolution of porosity

Porosity decreases with each PIP step after pyrolysis, but levels off at ~2.5% due to persistent voids

Distribution of porosity

top

distances are calculated relative to the bottom surface

bottom

ROI-1

Distribution of porosity

top

bottom

distances are calculated relative to the bottom surface

ROI-1

ROI-2

Connectivity of porosity

processing step	Through-thickness connectivity						
	C-Stage	Pyrolysis	PIP 1	PIP 2	PIP 3	PIP 4	PIP 5
ROI-1	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗
ROI-2	✓	✓	✓	-	✗	✗	✗

Filling of pore networks inhibits additional reduction of porosity after PIP 2

Inter- and intra-tow porosity

90° (red) and 0° (blue) fiber tows

Fiber tow segmentation using Avizo

inter-tow porosity

0.78 mm

intra-tow porosity

- 90° fiber tows
- 0° fiber tows
- inter-tow porosity
- intra-tow porosity

PIP 5

0.78 mm

Inter- and intra-tow porosity

90° (red) and 0° (blue) fiber tows

Fiber tow segmentation using Avizo

inter-tow porosity

0.78 mm

intra-tow porosity

PIP 5

- Most of the porosity forms in between tows
- Porosity resulting from pyrolysis is mostly filled with re-infiltration

Conclusions:

- It is possible to image the entire life-cycle of CMCs using Xray μ CT
- Evolution of porosity can be linked to specific PIP steps
 - The greatest reduction of porosity occurs between PIP 1-2
 - Small changes in porosity in steps PIP 3-5 are due to reduced connectivity between the free-surface and pores
 - Distribution of porosity in the laminate is relatively uniform and independent of processing steps
 - Most of porosity forms between tows

Future work:

- Classify porosity as voids or shrinkage cracks
- Develop automatic segmentation of individual fibers*
- Correlate damage evolution imaged during *in situ* testing to the microstructure (fibers, voids, shrinkage cracks)

*P. J. Creveling, *et al.* "A Fiber-segmentation Algorithm for Composites Imaged Using X-ray Microtomography: Development and Validation" Composites Part A (in review)

Thank You!

Questions?

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